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SOFC technology for heavy-duty vehicle propulsion

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Abstract

Solid oxide fuel cell (SOFC) systems can be integrated into heavy-duty vehicle (HDV) powertrains for applications where the vehicles are regularly and intensively used, such as commercial vehicles for long-haul road freight, as well as in buses, taxis, ships, etc. In such applications, cold-start of the fuel cell system is rare and current start-up times for the SOFC system are acceptable.

Using SOFCs for commercial vehicle applications allows for compatibility with the current trends towards LNG in freight transport. Given that natural gas can be replaced by synthetic natural gas (SNG) with carbon dioxide from biomass sources, a fully decarbonised and carbon neutral transport concept is achieved. The advantage over a pure low-temperature/hydrogen system is the higher efficiency of the fuel cell system, higher volumetric energy density of the fuel and the benefits of the high temperature off-heat. The phasing-in of such a system would occur without any disruption since it would use the current natural gas (methane) infrastructure. The application on commercial vehicles also includes refrigerated goods transport where the off-heat available from the SOFC system can power a vapour absorption refrigeration system.

This paper presents a zero-dimensional (0D) dynamic model of an SOFC stack with direct internal reforming (DIR) of methane, suitable for the integration into a vehicle powertrain. The area and number of cells define the stack size to meet the vehicle load requirements. The model uses an area specific resistance (ASR) approach to estimate polarisation losses and defines a lumped solid heat capacity to determine dynamic thermal response to a step change in load. The model shows good agreement with experimental data in the literature.

Introduction

Advantages of SOFC technology for vehicle propulsion

SOFCs are attractive for stationary power and heat applications, but there has been limited development in automotive SOFC systems. We identify a number of advantages of SOFCs for vehicle propulsion:

1. **High efficiency:** The electrical efficiency of an SOFC—system (64%, LHV, DC [1]) and stack (74% [2])—is significantly higher than that of an internal combustion engine (ICE) or polymer electrolyte fuel cell (PEFC), resulting in reduced fuel consumption and lower emissions.
2. **Fuel flexibility:** SOFC vehicles run on existing natural gas infrastructure. There are over 4000 CNG or LNG refuelling stations and 1.4 million NG vehicles in Europe [3]. Renewable energy and biomass-derived carbon dioxide can be co-electrolysed to produce the feedstock for synthetic natural gas (SNG) production. SOFC drivetrains with the phase-in of SNG offer a fully decarbonised transport solution.
3. **Electric:** The electric motor employed in electrified vehicles delivers high torque at low speeds, ideal for HDVs, giving superior performance to ICEs. A hybrid battery can be included to meet transient load requirements, enabling SOFC downsizing and energy recuperation.
4. **Off-heat availability:** High-temperature heat used for ancillary services, e.g. a vapour absorption refrigeration system [4] for refrigerated goods transport, or air conditioning for off-road construction vehicles.

Modelling of SOFCs in automotive applications

SOFCs have been demonstrated as an auxiliary power unit (APU) onboard diesel heavy-duty vehicles (HDVs) [5], and for battery charging onboard an electric car [6] or an electric bus [7]. A number of authors have simulated SOFC concept vehicles [8]–[11], typically focussing on the SOFC hybridisation strategy. To the author's knowledge, few have studied the SOFC thermal dynamics on a vehicle. To investigate this, an SOFC model is required.

We consider direct internal reforming (DIR) SOFCs advantageous to systems with external reforming, due to their lower system complexity and the cooling DIR provides to the stack through the endothermic methane steam reforming (MSR) reaction. Models of DIR-SOFCs often calculate the rate of MSR reaction on the SOFC anode with chemical kinetics, with the fast water-gas-shift (WGS) reaction at chemical equilibrium and the relatively slow CO oxidation neglected [12].

In a DIR-SOFC, current density, temperature and reactant profiles are non-linear, therefore partial pressures and chemical kinetics are challenging to determine accurately. A 0D modelling approach can simplify the model with two assumptions (i) that the MSR reaction goes to completion [13], and (ii) that the partial pressures in the stack are equal to those at the exit [14]. Two authors published hierarchical models to work around this limitation of 0D models with DIR [15], [16]. They reduced one-dimensional (1D) profiles to 0D averages to study the dynamic performance. This approach combined the accuracy of 1D modelling with the fast computation of 0D modelling; however, is valid only for fixed inlet conditions.

During standard operation of SOFCs, ohmic losses dominate over other polarisation losses due to the high operating temperature. Therefore, some 0D models employ a

temperature-dependent ASR approach that lumps all polarisation losses into a single linear correlation [17]. The ASR approach is useful for 0D grey-box modelling because it requires no knowledge of the SOFC geometry. However, the uniform current density assumed in 0D modelling means that the low and high current densities, seen in a 1D DIR-SOFC model at the stack entrance and exit, respectively, are not depicted in the model.

Many DIR-SOFC models calculate polarisation contributions separately. However, such models involve estimating parameters that are difficult to determine accurately and are specific to stack design. For example, many authors calculate ionic and electronic conductivities using experimental data from IEA benchmark testing for planar SOFCs [18] and from Siemens Westinghouse for tubular SOFCs [19], even if the SOFC stack they model is rather different.

Thermal dynamics are of interest to SOFC researchers since they have a large impact on SOFC degradation rates in transient operation. Some authors have neglected gas mass transfer and electrochemistry dynamics, since thermal dynamics are far slower and dominate SOFC transient behavior [16], [20].

To the authors' knowledge, experimental set-ups or models in the literature where the majority of methane is reformed internally are rare. However, such experimental data is required for model verification. Forschungszentrum Jülich (FZJ) ran long-term SOFC tests with 90% of methane reformed internally, however current-voltage behaviour was characterised only with wet hydrogen [21]. The Korea Institute of Energy Research (KIER) published the current-voltage behaviour of a FZJ 5 kW stack operating up to 3.5 atm (absolute) with 90% of methane reformed internally [22].

1. Scientific Approach

This paper presents a 0D DIR-SOFC model suitable for estimating the dynamic performance during transient operation onboard a vehicle, as depicted in Figure 1. The model has a number of assumptions:

- Current density, stack temperature and reactant profiles are all uniform,
- Gases in SOFC channels are ideal gas mixtures at constant pressure (at 1 atm),
- The SOFC operates adiabatically,
- Three internal reactions take place within the SOFC; MSR (1), WGS (2), and hydrogen oxidation (H₂OX) (3).
 - All methane fed to the stack reacts via MSR reaction [13],
 - The WGS reaction is at thermodynamic equilibrium [12],
 - Rate of CO oxidation is negligible [12],
- Only thermal dynamics are considered, pressure dynamics neglected [16]
 - Thermal mass of the fluid in the channels negligible to thermal solid mass,
- All polarisation losses may be approximated by a lumped ASR approach [17].

A steam-to-carbon ratio above two and an air-fuel equivalence ratio above three prevent carbon deposition. The stack operates at constant fuel utilisation. Single-cell experiments at FZJ estimated the ASR as a function of temperature [17]. The results of the model have been compared to experimental testing of the F' design FZJ stack at KIER [22].

Figure 1: SOFC modelling approach.

2. Experimental

The 0D DIR-SOFC model is described by Equations (4) to (15), with parameter values shown in Table 1. Table 2 shows the operating conditions for model verification, and Table 3 shows the conditions for investigating the transient response of the model.

Rate of reaction $r_{MSR} = \dot{n}_{CH_4,in}$ $r_{H_2O_X} = \frac{i}{nF}$ (4)

WGS equilibrium $K_{WGS} = \prod_i a_i v_{i,WGS} = \exp\left(-\frac{\Delta G_{WGS}^o(T)}{RT}\right)$ (5)

Material balance $\dot{n}_{i,out} = \dot{n}_{i,in} + v_{i,k} r_k$ (6)

The model calculates r_{WGS} by solving Equations (4) to (6).

Activity $a_i = y_i P_i = \frac{\dot{n}_{i,out}}{\sum_i \dot{n}_{i,out}} P_i$ (7)

Fuel utilisation $U_f = \frac{r_{H_2O_X}}{3 r_{MSR} + r_{WGS}}$ (8)

Cell voltage $V = V_0 - ASR \cdot i$ (9)

Nernst potential $V_0 = -\frac{\Delta G_{H_2O_X}^o(T)}{nF} - \frac{RT}{nF} \ln\left(\prod_i a_i v_{i,H_2O_X}\right)$ (10)

Area specific resistance $ASR = ASR_0 \cdot \exp\left[\frac{E_a}{R} \left(\frac{1}{T} - \frac{1}{T_0}\right)\right]$ (11)

Energy balance $m_s \widehat{C}_p \frac{dT}{dt} = \dot{E}_{in} - \dot{E}_{out} - Q - iV$ (12)

Energy flux in $\dot{E}_{in} = \dot{n}_{c,i,in} \cdot \int_{T_{ref}}^{T_{c,in}} C_{p,i}(T) dT + \dot{n}_{a,i,in} \cdot \int_{T_{ref}}^{T_{a,in}} C_{p,i}(T) dT$ (13)

Energy flux out $\dot{E}_{out} = \dot{n}_{i,out} \cdot \int_{T_{ref}}^{T_s} C_{p,i}(T) dT$ (14)

Heat of reaction $Q = r_k \cdot \Delta H_{r,i,k} = r_k \cdot \left[\left(\Delta H_{f,i} + \int_{T_{ref}}^{T_s} C_{p,i}(T) dT \right) v_{i,k} \right]$ (15)

Table 1: SOFC model parameters

Parameter	Value	
Area specific resistance at temperature T_0 , ASR_0	0.29 Ω cm ²	[17]
ASR reference temperature, T_0	1073 K	[17]
Activation energy of H ₂ OX reaction, E_a	0.65 eV	[17]
Mass of the solid per unit cell area, m_s	1.9 g cm ⁻²	
Specific heat capacity of fuel cell stack, \hat{C}_p	0.4 J g ⁻¹ K ⁻¹	[23]

Table 2: Experimental conditions for model verification [21]

Parameter	Value
Degree of pre-reforming	10%
LNG composition (simplification)	100% CH ₄
Steam-to-carbon ratio	2.1
Fuel utilisation	0.705
Air-fuel equivalence ratio	3
Temperature of air and fuel at stack inlet	700°C

Table 3: Simulation conditions for investigating transient response

Parameter	Value
Degree of pre-reforming	0%
LNG composition	100% CH ₄
Steam-to-carbon ratio	2
Fuel utilisation	0.70
Air-fuel equivalence ratio	6
Temperature of air and fuel at stack inlet	750°C

3. Results

SOFC characterisation

Overall, both the voltage and power characteristics show good agreement with the experimental data in Figure 2 at current densities of 0 A cm⁻² to 0.44 A cm⁻² with the stack temperature at 750°C. The point of inflection in voltage displayed around 0.03 A cm⁻² is unexpected. It could be an artefact of the model caused by poor estimation of polarisation at low current densities using the ASR approach. However, this behaviour is acceptable, since it is outside the normal operational range of an SOFC stack. DIR reduces the Nernst potential (10) relative to operation with hydrogen fuel. The approximation that the uniform molar composition in the fuel channel is equal to that at the stack outlet, may be inaccurate, altering the Nernst potential, and shifting the voltage characteristic in Figure 2 vertically.

The gradient of the voltage characteristic is the ASR, a function of temperature. The parameters of the ASR equation (11)(11) were determined from single cell experiments at FZJ at low fuel utilisations and constant temperature [17]. Whilst cell-level results may have limited accuracy in predicting stack-level behaviour, the results in Figure 2 suggest they are useful to estimate the trend.

In Figure 2, the voltage and power calculated by the model are lower than the experimental data, particularly at higher current densities. It would be useful to have

experimental data under different operating conditions and at higher current densities (at least up to 1 A cm^{-2}) to better validate the model.

Overall, the SOFC model matches the experimental data well, suggesting that the model is suitable for integration into an electric drivetrain model.

SOFC dynamic response

A step increase in current density from 0.4 A cm^{-2} to 0.7 A cm^{-2} is simulated under the operating conditions tabulated in Table 3. Figure 3 shows a temperature increase of 25°C in response to the step increase in current density. The increased rate of the electrochemical oxidation of hydrogen, which is an exothermic reaction, causes this increase in temperature.

Figure 4 shows an immediate voltage drop of 0.096 V in response to the step in current density. The increased polarisation losses that occur at increased load cause this drop in voltage. However, as the temperature of the stack increases, the ASR decreases and the voltage recovers by 0.025 V .

The relaxation time of the voltage and temperature response is analysed using the approach used in Sorrentino et al. [16]. The authors defined relaxation time as the time to recover 90% of the voltage drop, and 90% of the temperature increase, respectively. The voltage relaxation time is 650 s and the temperature relaxation time is 690 s .

The magnitude of the temperature and voltage response is dependent not only on the load change and on the ASR, but also on the chemical reaction kinetics and operating point (temperature, inlet composition, etc.). The relaxation time is dependent on the estimated mass and heat capacity of the stack (12). The relaxation times here are of similar order of magnitude to simulations presented in Sorrentino et al. [16].

Similar stack current step experiments conducted for an SOFC stack within an insulated integrated system module (ISM) from SOLIDPower SA, indicated relaxation times one to two orders of magnitude higher [14] due to the far larger thermal mass of system components in the HotBox, which is not considered in this simulation.

Figure 2: Verification of voltage and power characteristics.

Figure 3: Temperature response to step change in current.

Figure 4: Voltage response to step change in current.

Conclusions

This paper displays a DIR-SOFC stack model suitable for integration into a system model on a commercial vehicle, with good agreement with experimental data in the literature. The results presented the thermal response of the stack during transient operation, which acts as a constraint in an SOFC control strategy. Additionally, only the current density, the number of cells and the cell area need be defined to meet a required load cycle.

However, there are some limitations to the thermal model: (i) the assumption that outlet temperatures on the anode- and cathode-side are equal and (ii) the 0D modelling approach does not account for temperature gradients within the stack. Moreover, the SOFC system from KIER used for experimental validation is significantly heavier than a system suitable for integration on-board a vehicle.

The lumped 0D modelling approach has the advantage of being computationally quick and requires knowledge of a limited number of variables. Therefore, it is considered an efficient means to estimate the behaviour of an SOFC within a vehicle drivetrain.

Nomenclature

a	activity, species i	
ASR	area specific resistance	$\Omega \text{ m}^2$
ASR_0	area specific resistance at temperature T_0	$\Omega \text{ m}^2$
C_p	molar heat capacity of species i	$\text{J mol}^{-1} \text{ K}^{-1}$
\widehat{C}_p	specific heat capacity of fuel cell stack	$\text{J kg}^{-1} \text{ K}^{-1}$
E_a	activation energy of H ₂ OX reaction	J mol^{-1}
\dot{E}	enthalpy rate	J s^{-1}
F	Faradays constant	C mol^{-1}
G°	Gibbs free energy of reaction k at standard pressure	J mol^{-1}
i	current density	A m^{-2}
K	equilibrium constant, reaction k	
m_s	mass of the fuel cell stack per unit area	kg m^{-2}
n	moles of electrons transferred per mole H ₂ OX reaction	
\dot{n}	molar flow rate, species i	$\text{mol s}^{-1} \text{ m}^{-2}$
P	partial pressure	Pa
R	universal molar gas constant	$\text{J mol}^{-1} \text{ K}^{-1}$
r	rate of reaction, reaction k	$\text{mol s}^{-1} \text{ m}^{-2}$
T	temperature	K
T_0	ASR reference temperature	K
T_{ref}	enthalpy reference temperature	K
U_f	fuel utilisation	
V	cell voltage	V
V_0	open circuit voltage	V
ν	stoichiometric coefficient, species i , reaction k	

Subscripts

a	anode-side
e	electric
c	cathode-side
i	species i
in	inlet
k	reaction k
out	outlet
s	stack

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